

Decreasing Charge Losses in Perovskite Solar Cells Through mp-TiO₂/MAPI Interface Engineering

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On the basis of our experience in controlling the recombination kinetics in Dye Sensitized Solar Cells (DSSC) by modifying the mesoporous TiO₂ (mp-TiO₂) interface we modified the methyl ammonium lead iodide (MAPI) /mp-TiO₂ interface with a nanoscopic layer of insulating Al₂O₃. The effects on device efficiency, the open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), device reproducibility and the relationship between the increase in V_{oc} and the presence of the Al₂O₃ layer is thoroughly discussed and explained. Although in DSSC there is a TiO₂ conduction band edge shift for Al₂O₃ coated mp-TiO₂ films, in MAPI perovskite solar cells the charge vs voltage measurements carried out under sun-simulated irradiation conditions show a negligible shift of the exponential charge distribution whether it is measured using PICE (Photo Induced Charge Extraction) or PIDC (Photo Induced Differential Charging). Furthermore, the charge recombination lifetime decreases considerably in the Al₂O₃-treated samples, which improves the overall efficiency of the device because of the slower rate in the back-electron transfer reactions.

Introduction

The use of methyl ammonium lead iodide (MAPI) perovskite-type semiconductor material has been the focus of increasing interest for the development of efficient solar cells.¹⁻³ In less than 5 years solar-to-electrical conversion efficiency has increased from $\eta=3.8\%$ ⁴ efficiencies to almost 20%,⁵ which exceeds the best efficiencies measured for other so-called third-generation solar cells such as DSSC⁶ (Dye Sensitized Solar Cells), OSC⁷ (Organic Solar Cells) and QDSC⁸ (Quantum Dot Solar Cells). The easy-to-fabricate procedures, the low cost of the materials and past experience of these solar cell technologies have paved the way for MAPI solar cells to become a *hot spot* in materials science for energy conversion devices such as solar cells and light-emitting diodes.⁹ Moreover, the recent discovery that MAPI can be used as a semiconductor for solar cells has also presented such novel scientific challenges as explaining the unusually large amount of measured charge in MAPI solar cells,¹⁰ the presence of hysteresis effects,¹¹⁻¹⁴ the bi-exponential nature of the small-perturbation based V_{oc} decays^{15, 16} and/or the presence of interfacial dipoles.^{17, 18} The increase in solar cell efficiency has been spectacular, and the improvement is far superior than that experienced in such other solar-cell technologies as CdTe and CIS.¹⁹ However, the exact mechanisms that enable sunlight to be efficiently con-

verted into electrical current have not been examined in such depth – although there are some exceptions^{16, 20-23} – and there is still the scientific challenge of getting MAPI solar cells to perform to their maximum theoretical efficiency by reducing non-radiative charge recombination losses,²⁴ improving spectral response²⁵ and increasing operational stability.²⁶

The semiconductor thin film in MAPI perovskite solar cells can be used in device configurations that: (a) have mesoporous metal oxide scaffolds with Al₂O₃, TiO₂ or ZnO²⁷ contacts, (b) do not have the mesoporous scaffold and (c) use organic materials as selective contacts.²⁸ Nonetheless, it is worth mentioning that, as far as we know, the best certified devices have the archetypal device configuration⁵ of FTO/d-TiO₂/mp-TiO₂/MAPI/HTM/Au, where FTO is the fluorine-doped tin oxide semiconductor layer deposited on glass, d-TiO₂ is a thinner (~50nm) dense layer of TiO₂, mp-TiO₂ is a thin mesoporous layer (~450nm) and the HTM is the organic hole transport material. The metal contact is usually gold (Au) in this class of device architecture too.

For the reasons given below the device configuration described above is the standard used in this work unless otherwise stated: on the one hand, our experience in the deposition of the TiO₂ metal oxide,²⁹ its characterization and previous encouraging results in relation with this

work using this device structure¹⁵ and, on the other hand, to clarify further the role on the mp-TiO₂ layer in the MAPI perovskite solar cell.

It is well known that if the efficiency of the solar cell is to be increased, the charge losses due to inconvenient interfacial charge recombination reactions under operation need to be reduced.³⁰ In past studies with DSSC, we observed that direct back-electron transfer from the photo-injected electrons at the mp-TiO₂ to the oxidized electrolyte was one of the major issues that had to be overcome if solar cell efficiency was to be improved. Indeed, reducing this particular charge recombination reaction through better dye design and rational interface engineering leads to better and more reproducible DSSC.³¹

In our first communication on the MAPI perovskite semiconductor in solar cells,¹⁵ we hypothesized that several interfacial and band-to-band recombination pathways can be found in MAPI/mp-TiO₂/HTM samples (see Scheme 1). In one, after electron injection from the MAPI to the TiO₂ conduction band (reaction 3, Scheme 1) subsequent interfacial back electron transfer may take place (reaction 6, Scheme 1). In another, the photo-injected electrons at the TiO₂ can also recombine with holes at the oxidized HTM (analogously to the reaction occurring in solid-state DSSC but in this case there cannot be a direct recombination as there is a thin layer of MAPI perovskite between the TiO₂ and the HTM) and as measured by Moser and co-workers using laser transient absorption spectroscopy²⁰ (reaction 5, Scheme 1). Moreover, electrons at the MAPI perovskite can also recombine with the holes at the oxidized HTM (reaction 4, Scheme 1). Last but not least, band-to-band non-radiative and radiative charge recombination reactions at the MAPI perovskite (reaction 2 and 1, Scheme 1) have to be considered as well as possible charge recombination reactions between electrons at the MAPI and recombination states at the TiO₂ (reaction 7, Scheme 1).

Hence, the modification of the mp-TiO₂/MAPI perovskite interface may affect at least one of the recombination pathways that limit the performance of the solar cell.

The use of conformally deposited insulating overlayers onto the TiO₂ nanocrystal surfaces has been previously explored by our group and others in DSSC.³²⁻³⁴ Indeed, it has been demonstrated that interfacial engineering on the semiconductor nanocrystals, either TiO₂ or ZnO, substantially decreases the charge losses due to interfacial recombination processes. In fact, a recent publication³⁵ by Jung and co-workers describes the use of MgO on mp-TiO₂ in MAPI solar cells, although how the device should be electronically characterized so that the changes in solar cell Voc can be understood remained unclear.

In the present study we have fabricated MAPI perovskite solar cells with the archetypal structure mentioned above as well as MAPI perovskite solar cells with an Al₂O₃ insulating thin layer on the nanocrystalline TiO₂ particles that conform the mp-TiO₂ layer. The former will be referred to throughout the paper as MAPI perovskite solar cells, while the latter will be referred to as Al₂O₃-coated perovskite solar cells. We have also used advanced photo-induced characterization techniques: namely, photo-induced transient photo-voltage (PIT-PV), photo-induced differential charging (PIDC) and photo-induced transient photo-current (PIT-PC) to thoroughly analyse the differences in charge density (defined as the total accumulated

charge in the device at a given bias), the charge recombination lifetime and the relationship between both parameters. The findings described below are key to (a) understanding the device charge recombination processes that hamper the solar-to-electrical conversion efficiency and (b) increasing the reproducibility of device fabrication through interface engineering.

Scheme 1. The photo-induced interfacial charge transfer recombination reactions in MAPI perovskite solar cells; (1) band-to-band radiative recombination, (2) band-to-band non radiative recombination, (3) interfacial electron transfer from MAPI conduction band (CB) to TiO₂ and (4) interfacial electron transfer from the MAPI CB to the HTM, (5) interfacial electron transfer from TiO₂ CB to the HTM, (6) interfacial electron transfer from the TiO₂ CB to the MAPI and (7) interfacial electron transfer from the MAPI CB to TiO₂ surface states (s.s.).

Experimental Section

Device preparation

The FTO- (Fluorine-doped Tin Oxide) coated glasses (resistance= 8Ω/cm²) were etched using Zn powder (Alfa Aesar 98%) and a 2 M solution of HCl according to the desired pattern. The substrates were then cleaned for 15 minutes in an ultrasound bath with deionized water with Hellmax soap, with de-ionized water and finally with ethanol. The substrates were dried and a UV/Ozone treatment was performed for 20 minutes.

A solution of 0.65 mL of Ti (IV) isopropoxide (Sigma Aldrich 97%) and 0.38 mL of acetylacetone (Sigma Aldrich) were mixed in 5 mL of ethanol. This solution was spun-casted at 3000 rpm for 60s over the FTO. The substrates were calcined at 500°C for 30 min to obtain the titanium oxide dense layer. Afterwards, titanium oxide-coated substrates were immersed in a 40 mM TiCl₄ solution at 70°C for 30 minutes. Then, the substrates were cleaned with water and ethanol and heated at 390°C for 20 minutes.

A mixture of TiO₂ paste (Ti Nanoxide HT/SP Solaronix) and ethanol 2:5 (w:w) was spin-coated at 5000 rpm for 30 seconds. The substrates were heated using the following temperature sequence: 325°C, 30 min/375°C, 5 min/

450°C, 15 min/500°C, 30 min. In all cases, the substrates were placed inside the glovebox for further steps immediately after the heat treatment to keep moisture away from the samples (see below).

The alumina coating step was carried out as reported by Palomares et al. In brief, 3 mL of 3 M aluminum tri-*sec*-butoxide (Sigma Aldrich®) and 17 mL of dry *i*PrOH (Sigma Aldrich ©) were mixed to obtain a 0.15 M solution and it was stirred and heated in the glove box at 70°C for 20 minutes. Then, the mp-TiO₂ coated substrates were immersed in the solution at 70°C for 20 minutes and rinsed with *i*PrOH. Afterwards, the substrates were heated to 435°C for 30 minutes.

The methylammonium iodide was synthesized as described previously.³⁶

To deposit the perovskite, a 3:1 molar ratio solution of methylammonium iodide and PbCl₂ (Sigma Aldrich © 98%) was prepared in DMF (dimethyl formamide). The perovskite precursor was deposited by spin-coating over the mp-TiO₂ layer at 2000 rpm for 1 min. The as-deposited substrates were heated at 120°C for 30 minutes, and their colour changed from yellow to black. The measured UV-Visible spectra on mp-TiO₂/MAPI and Al₂O₃-coated mp-TiO₂/MAPI samples do not show significant absorption changes within the range measured.

The spiro-OMeTAD (1-Material ©), the HTM, was dissolved in chlorobenzene (CBZ) to reach 70 mg/mL. Also, 28.8 µL of *t*BuPyr (tert-butylpyridine) and 17.5 µL of a 520 mg/mL of a LiTFSI solution in acetonitrile were added to the OMeTAD solution as additives. The HTM layer was deposited by spin-coating the solution onto the perovskite at 2000 rpm for 1 minute.

Finally, 80 nm of gold metal was evaporated at the anode by thermal evaporation at a pressure no higher than 1x10⁻⁶ mbar.

All the steps for the alumina coating and the perovskite and HTM deposition were carried out inside the glove box to avoid humidity ([O₂] < 100 ppm and [H₂O] < 0.1 ppm).

Current vs voltage (JV) measurements

The solar cell performances were measured with a Sun 200 solar simulator (150 W, ABET Technologies) with the appropriate filters to simulate the AM 1.5G solar spectrum. A silicon diode was used to set the illumination intensity to 100mWm⁻². The potential and cell current were measured with a Keithley © 2400 digital source meter.

Time-resolved photo-induced measurements.

All photo-induced measurement techniques such as PICE (photo-induced charge extraction, PIT-PV (photo-induced transient photovoltage), PIT-PC (photo-induced transient photocurrent) and PIDC (photo-induced differential charging) are described with system diagrams in Supplementary Information.

Results and Discussion

Device characterization

Figure 1 illustrates the current density vs voltage measurements (IV curves) for archetypal MAPI perovskite solar

cells and the Al₂O₃-coated cells under standard sun-simulated irradiation (100mW/cm², 1.5 AM G).

Figure 1. Several MAPI perovskite solar cells with and without the Al₂O₃-modified mp-TiO₂/MAPI interface under 1 sun illumination and the corresponding dark curves (dashed lines)

As can be seen in Figure 1, Al₂O₃ mp-TiO₂ coated MAPI perovskite solar cells show an increase in Voc and photocurrent, which leads to an average efficiency of $\eta_{Al_2O_3}=12\%$ in contrast to standard MAPI perovskite solar cells, which have a standard average efficiency of $\eta=10.2\%$. Table 1 lists all the relevant parameters for the cells measured in this study.

Table 1.1 Most relevant parameters obtained from the IV curves illustrated in Figure 1

Device number	Voc (mV)	Jsc (mA/cm ²)	FF (%) ²	η (%)	Al ₂ O ₃ -coated
Cell 1	920	18.6	67.8	11.6	yes
Cell 2	960	20.1	66.1	12.7	yes
Cell 3	939	19.3	65.1	11.8	yes
Cell 4	870	17.6	67.9	10.4	no
Cell 5	870	17.0	72.3	10.7	no
Cell 6	860	15.0	73.6	9.5	no

¹Solar cell area of 0.25cm². All solar cells were fabricated and measured under the same conditions at forward bias.

²Device fill factor.

Further measurements of solar cells (Figure 2) fabricated on different days and in different conditions, as the devices depicted and listed in Figure 1 and Table 1 respectively, but always keeping identical measurement and fabrication conditions within each set of samples of Al₂O₃ coated mp-TiO₂ and the corresponding MAPI perovskite solar cells as control show identical trend with the Al₂O₃ modified mp-TiO₂/MAPI interface having higher Voc and, in average, higher solar-to-energy conversion efficiency.

Figure 2. Solar cell open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) distribution for 28 Al₂O₃-coated mp-TiO₂ devices (grey) and 27 MAPI perovskite solar cells (red). Top, devices measured under reverse bias. Bottom, devices measured under forward bias.

To understand the effect of the Al₂O₃ on the mp-TiO₂ and the overall solar cell performance and for purposes of comparison with DSSC we carried out the experiments described below. Photo-induced differential charging (PIDC) was used to analyse the accumulated charge in the solar cell under different light-biases (solar cell voltage induced by different illumination intensities) in DSSC,³⁷ QDSC,³⁸ OSC³⁹ and, more recently, MAPI solar cells.¹⁶ It also enabled us to compare the photo-generated charge density, at the same V_{oc}, and the charge recombination lifetime of different types of solar cell.

Photo-Induced Differential Charging (PIDC)

The PIDC technique is described in the Supplementary information of this manuscript. In brief, the charge is measured using PIT-PV and PIT-PC (photo-induced transient photo-current) as our group and others have demonstrated elsewhere.⁴⁰ The use of PIDC is particularly necessary when the PICE decay has a longer lifetime than the PIT-PV decay measured at 1 sun (as it does in the MAPI perovskite solar cells in Figure 3).

Figure 3. PICE decay (black line) for a MAPI perovskite solar cell and the PIT-PV transient (blue line) after sun-simulated illumination equivalent to 1 sun. Notice the different time scales for the PICE (bottom axis) and the PIT-PV (top axis).

To estimate the photo-generated charge stored in the MAPI perovskite solar cell we must assume that (a) the solar cell has no charge losses at short circuit and (b) the PIT-PC under 1 sun and in the dark are similar. In other words, the charge generation efficiency is similar in short-circuit and open-circuit solar cell conditions. Figure 4 shows the PIT-PC measurements for both types of MAPI perovskite solar cell.

Figure 4. PIT-PC decays measured for (top) mpTiO₂/MAPI perovskite and (bottom) Al₂O₃/mpTiO₂/MAPI perovskite solar cells

As can be seen in Figure 4, the PIT-PCs under 1 sun or in the dark for both types of solar cell are quite close. Hence, we carried out the PIDC for both types of solar cell devices. Figure 5 illustrates the charge measured from the PIDC vs solar cell voltage.

Figure 5. Charge measured using PIDC at different solar cell voltages from MAPI perovskite solar cells and Al_2O_3 -coated perovskite solar cells. Cell 3A has been removed for purposes of clarity.

Unlike previous measurements of DSSC with the Al_2O_3 coating, there is no clear and reproducible shift between the exponential curves measured.⁴¹ In DSSC with the mp-TiO₂ conformally coated with Al_2O_3 a shift of the measured charge vs voltage exponential curve is observed and assigned to a shift of the TiO₂ conduction band edge with concomitant shift of the quasi-Fermi level for the electrons at the mp-TiO₂. The mp-TiO₂ conduction band shift plus the slower interfacial recombination kinetics between the electrons at the mp-TiO₂ and the oxidized electrolyte, in DSSC, increase the open circuit voltage of the DSSC. Subsequently, the PIT-PV in the MAPI perovskite solar cells was measured to see if there is a correlation with the measured higher open-circuit voltage.

Photo-Induced Transient Photovoltage (PIT-PV)

The PIT-PV technique has been widely used to correlate the measured charge, at a given voltage, with the charge recombination lifetime. In a seminal paper,⁴² Bisquert and Zaban defined the Voc decay technique for DSSC and our group and others subsequently used a modified version of the technique (see Supplementary Information), which is based on a small perturbation of the open-circuit cell voltage using a fast light pulse. The fast pulse disrupts the equilibrium and raises the quasi-Fermi level for the electrons at the mp-TiO₂, which is restored after the pulse finishes at the original energy level and restores the initial open-circuit voltage. In DSSC, the voltage decay promoted by the fast light pulse results in a mono-exponential decay with an amplitude that is always smaller than 10mV to ensure a minor perturbation of the cell open-circuit voltage.

Figure 6 illustrates the PIT-PV decays for our MAPI perovskite solar cells.

Figure 6. Measured PIT-PV for a MAPI perovskite solar cell (black) and an Al_2O_3 -coated MAPI perovskite solar cell (red) at $100\text{mW}/\text{cm}^2$ light irradiation. The inset shows the fastest component of the PIT-PV.

The first difference with the PIT-PV decays in DSSC is the bi-exponential nature of the decays measured with both the Al_2O_3 coating and the MAPI perovskite as controls. As shown in Figure 6 both samples show bi-exponential decays with $\tau_1 = 175 \mu\text{s}$ (20%) and $\tau_2 = 3 \mu\text{s}$ (80%) for Al_2O_3 -coated solar cells and $\tau_1 = 73 \mu\text{s}$ (20%) and $\tau_2 = 0.8 \mu\text{s}$ (80%) for MAPI perovskite solar cells with a similar charge density $\sim 35\text{nC}/\text{cm}^2$. This result is in good agreement with previous data.^{16, 23}

In MAPI perovskite solar cells, the origin of the high photovoltage measured, which in some cases is above 1V, is still far from clear. Moreover, the considerable differences in charge density measured using PICE (see Supplementary Information) and PIDC and the different chemical nature that both types of charges can have, taking into account the differences in the kinetics from the bi-exponential PIT-PV decay, makes assigning the processes that give rise to the accumulated charges measured even more challenging. It may well be that the measured transient photovoltage does not correspond to a charge recombination process (charge losses) but to a reorganization of dipoles at the MAPI (for example) which changes the voltage or to a combination of both processes. Nevertheless, we studied the PIT-PV in detail and we suggest that the fast component of the PIT-PV decay is the product of the electron-hole recombination process and, therefore, the photo-induced charge recombination lifetime.¹⁶ Hence, on the basis of our past experience, for purposes of comparing MAPI solar cells we used the charge measured by PIDC and the fastest component of the PIT-PV decay.

Charge recombination lifetime vs charge density

It is important to notice that, for the comparison, we use the charge measured by PIDC, instead of the cell Voc measured at different light intensities (so called light bias) because different solar cells –DSSC, OPV and QDSC – can have very different amounts of charge stored at the same Voc. Therefore, the compared charge recombination lifetime will be neither meaningful nor appropriate. Figure 7 illustrates the carrier recombination lifetime vs electrical charge for both types of solar cell.

Figure 7. Non-radiative carrier recombination lifetime (fast component PIT-PV decay) vs solar cell electrical charge measured by PIDC. The numbers correspond to the recombination order factor (OF).

As illustrated in Figure 7, the Al_2O_3 conformal coating leads to slower interfacial charge recombination lifetimes than the standard mpTiO₂ film.

We would also like to emphasize that although the slowest component of the PIT-PV decay, either with the charge measured using PICE or the charge measured using PIDC, cannot fairly reproduce the J_{rec} (data shown in the Supplementary Information, Table S1) and, thus, seems that is not related to the “electrical charge” (understanding as *electrical charge* electrons and holes) at the MAPI perovskite still accounts for at least 20% of the PIT-PV decay and, interestingly the PIT-PV slow component of the decay is slower for Al_2O_3 . The two types of solar cell – Al_2O_3 -coated and MAPI perovskite – are compared in Figure 8.

Figure 8. The slow component for the PIT-PV decays vs solar cell charge measured by PIDC at different light biases. The numbers correspond to the recombination order factor (OF).

Conclusions

We used Al_2O_3 conformal coating from solution-processed methods on mesoporous TiO₂ electrodes (mpTiO₂) to prepare efficient MAPI perovskite solar cells. The Al_2O_3 coating improves the solar-cell efficiency mainly due to a higher open circuit voltage (V_{oc}). The increase in V_{oc} is systematic and reproducible. We also studied interfacial charge recombination processes using photo-induced time resolved methods in complete devices under sun-simulated irradiation conditions. The clear shift found in the exponential charge distribution when $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{mpTiO}_2$ coated DSSC was used was not observed with PIDC.

The analysis of the PIT-PV decays shows two different time components, in good agreement with previous measurements with other MAPI perovskite solar cells. In fact, for Al_2O_3 coated solar cells both time components present in the PIT-PV decay are slower than the standard MAPI perovskite solar cell. A careful comparison of both charge recombination lifetime components at the same charge density further confirms that the recombination lifetime for Al_2O_3 treated solar cells is significantly slower.

Hence, it seems clear that the slower charge recombination kinetics in the Al_2O_3 -coated MAPI perovskite solar cells can be directly correlated with the solar cell V_{oc} improvement. However, unlike DSSC, it was unclear why both PIT-PV time components are affected by the presence of the Al_2O_3 coating on the mesoporous TiO₂. A feasible hypothesis in the light of the results obtained in this study is that both PIT-PV components can be assigned to two different charge recombination processes: *a)* the charge transfer of electrons from the TiO₂, after electron transfer from the MAPI perovskite under illumination, with the holes at the HTM, and *b)* charge recombination between electrons at the TiO₂ with holes at the MAPI perovskite. In both cases the Al_2O_3 acts as a physical barrier (as it does in the case of DSSC) that decreases the rate of the back electron transfer reaction after photo-induced electron injection from the MAPI perovskite to the TiO₂ CB.

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ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting information contains PICE, voltage stability and PIT-PV measurement. A detailed description of the PICE and PIT-PV systems and an HRTEM image of the coated and uncoated Al_2O_3 nanoparticles. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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